

Dependance of Learning Styles on Age and Nationality

Ortikova Tursunoy

Middle-level doctoral student of Gulistan State University

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Oct 2024; **Published:** 16 Nov 2024

Abstract: This article analysis a link between age, nationality factors and learning styles. As well, it shows several key points and causes of an influence by the two factors on learning preferences. The research aim is to define the dependance of students' information acquisition on several main elements and aids to organize effective language learning process by uncovering depending sides of stylistic preferences.

Keywords: learning styles, age relatedness, nationality, education system, young learners, sensory experiences, auditory, kinesthetic, visual learners, information receivers, learning new concepts, stylistic preferences, language acquisition.

Introduction

In common sense, since age and its impact on language learning has become a usual topic of many scientific researches, it is hardly a new topic. Specifically, several scientific works dedicated to an issue of early language or late language learners have been done by Simone Pfenninger and David Singleton, Natakorn Satienchayakorn. Besides, Emre Guvendir and Bahiyyih Hardacre researched the listening aspect with different age groups. However, it is necessary to uncover the area regarding regional and age relatedness to learning styles. For the reason that it is a less discovered side of language acquisition, the research aims to suggest and analysis that there is a connection between style variables and the factors above. A Cambridge book namely *Lessons from Good Language Learners* (edited by Carol Griffiths) has been used as a main source for this article.

Methodology and used literature

The way that the research work has been conducted is a quantitative method, specifically a Correlational Research. In the first step to reach enough and intended outcomes several useful articles by Mr. Sreenidhi S K and Ms. Tay Chinyi Helena on learning styles in different scientists' views, scientific book by Cambridge University press has been studied and deeply analyzed. During the process, various viewpoints about age and nationality in multiple scientific works have been generalized and the fact that there is a relationship between age, nationality and learning styles has been revealed.

Historical background

The roots of the earliest theories about the different ways people assimilate information trace back to the year 1904. Following this, more detailed research into these theories continued in 1907. However, until 1950, there were almost no significant studies conducted on this theory. The most recent categorization of this theory, widely used today, is N.D. Fleming's VAK model [1, 137–55]. According to this well-known theory, information receivers are divided

into three groups: visual learners (those who learn by seeing), auditory learners (those who learn by hearing), and kinesthetic or tactile learners (those who learn through movement or touch).

The VAK model, considered the result of long years of research, helps improve the effectiveness of the learning process by considering which type of learning is dominant in a learner, based on their unique characteristics.

Age and learning style

A learner's preferred method of learning is indirectly connected to their age, gender, specific circumstances, and physical condition. For instance, if we focus on the age factor, it can be observed that younger learners tend to learn by interacting with the surrounding knowledge through physical or hands-on activities. Other types of information reception typically develop at an older age [2, 18].

Additionally, it should be noted that many younger learners belong to both kinesthetic and visual learning groups. Young children tend to develop visual ways of processing information before they can understand it verbally [3]. This is because that they rely on sensory-based experiences in which they apply mixed sensory-driven styles (kinesthetic, auditory, visual) at the same time to comprehend new concept. As they get older, they start choosing one type of learning style over others. To elaborate on the relationship between learning types and age, each learning type has its own internal subdivision related to age. For example, when discussing visual information reception, as mentioned earlier, simple forms such as pictures, videos, and visual texts are easier to comprehend, while more complex forms such as diagrams and drawings are a bit more challengeable.

In this context, it can be said that simpler forms of visual learning, like using pictures, are more characteristic of younger children, whereas visual learning methods using diagrams and charts are more suitable and effective for older students.

Picture 1. Modes of visualization depending on age.

Simple forms

As it is shown in the illustration above, a single visual learning style consists of two separate subclasses. Ages differ according to sophisticated and unsophisticated groups of visuals due to the fact that cognitive process occurs dissimilarly in different age phases.

The role of nationality

It is undoubtful that learning styles are influenced by nations and one of them among them can be predominant as a way of learning as different cultures and countries have various philosophies towards education system. Here are several key points which have an impact on learning styles.

Differences in education systems

It is definitely fact that distinct teaching methods and approaches are used in a specific

Complex forms

country. For instance, many East-Asian nations mostly rely on memory-based or lecture-dominant lessons as a result of which students with such national backgrounds tend to acquire information by hearing (*auditory learners*). In fact, most western countries organize collaborative, experiential and discussion driven lessons which means westerners learn new concepts by doing (*kinesthetic learners*).

Technology and media

In most modern countries as technology has considerably developed, learning and teaching processes occur through using multimedia tools. They invest more money in digital education tools and interactive technologies, which encourages multimedia-based and visual learning.

Nationality among a great many factors may have an impact on students' stylistic preferences as stated above and the topic of multiple research works has been dedicated. For example, the result of the research by Reid (1987) shows that Korean students came out to be visual learners [4, 87-111] as well as Rossie-Le's Vietnamese students (1995) [5, 118-125] whereas auditory learning style became dominant in Arabic and Chinese language learners. Although a noticeable relationship has been identified between nationality and styles of information reception, it cannot be overgeneralized. Any language learner had better adapt multiple learning styles in any condition as long as learning can occur in a successful manner [6,51].

Conclusion

Age influences learning styles through changes in cognitive development, previous experiences, and physical factors such as memory and attention. Younger learners are more sensory-driven and concrete in their thinking, while older learners tend to prefer strategic, experience-based, and reflective learning. As such, learning styles adapt to the cognitive and life-stage needs of the individual, and these shifts are important to consider when designing educational process. The dependence of learning styles on nationality is formed by a union of cultural values, educational systems, and societal norms. While certain national or cultural trends may influence learning preferences, individual factors such as personality, prior experiences, and personal preferences often play an even more significant role.

References

1. Fleming, N.D., Mills, C. (1992). Not Another Inventory, Rather a Catalyst for reflection to improve the academy. Professional and Organisational Development Network in Higher Education. pp. 137–55.
2. Mr. Sreenidhi S K, Ms. Tay Chinyi Helena, “Styles of Learning Based on the Research of Fernald, Keller, Orton, Gillingham, Stillman, Montessori and Neil D Fleming”. International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field Issn – 2455-0620 Volume - 3, Issue - 4, Apr – 2017. P 18.
3. Barry, A.M. (1997). Visual intelligence, perception, image, and manipulation in visual communication. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press.
4. Reid, J.M. The learning style preferences in ESL students. *TESOL Quarterly*, 21(1), 87-111.
5. Rossie-Le, L. (1995) Learning styles and strategies in adult immigrant ESL students. In J.M. Reid (ed.), *Learning styles in ESL/EFL Classroom*, Boston, MA: Heinle & Heinle, 118-125.
6. Griffiths, C. (2009). *Lessons from Good Language Learners*. Cambridge University Press, pp 38-51.